

JAWAHARLAL NEHRU COLLEGE,

Pasighat East-siang District , A.P

Session:2024-25

Department of Mathematics

MAT-DE-367: DISSERTATION

Mathematical Motivation, Competency, and Technology

Impact: A Case Study

Sub-topic:

**“Real-World Applications of Mathematics: Perspectives from
Local Vendors”**

Submitted by:

Name: Omik Panggam

Class: B.Sc 6th Semester

Roll No: 22MAT-01-030

Under the Supervision :

Dr. Gete Umbrey

Assistant Professor,

Department of Mathematics,
Jawaharlal Nehru College, Pasighat

Date of Submission: 03 June 2025

Certificate

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Real-World Applications of Mathematics: Perspectives from Local Vendors**” submitted by **Omik Panggam**, a student of B.Sc. Mathematics, Jawaharlal Nehru College, Pasighat, has been carried out under my supervision.

The dissertation is a record of original research work based on direct surveys and observations conducted among local vendors in Pasighat. It reflects the student’s own efforts and critical analysis of the mathematical practices used in real-life business activities by individuals of varied educational backgrounds.

I find the work to be satisfactory and recommend it for submission as a part of the curriculum requirement.

Student’s Signature

Omik Panggam
B.Sc. (Mathematics)
J.N. College, Pasighat

Supervisor’s Signature

Dr. Gete Umbrey
Assistant Professor,
Department of Mathematics,
J.N. College, Pasighat

Declaration

I, Omik Panggam, hereby declare that the dissertation entitled “**Real-World Applications of Mathematics: Perspectives from Local Vendors**” submitted to the Department of Mathematics, Jawaharlal Nehru College, Pasighat, is a genuine record of original work carried out by me under the supervision of Dr. Gete Umbrey, Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, J.N. College, Pasighat.

The findings, observations, and results presented in this dissertation are based on primary data collected through surveys and personal interaction with local vendors. This work has not been submitted to any other institution or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all the local vendors who generously participated in this study and shared their valuable insights. Their contributions were vital to the successful completion of this research.

I am deeply thankful to my project supervisor **Dr. Gete Umbrey** for his consistent guidance, thoughtful feedback, and unwavering support throughout the course of this work.

I also extend my appreciation to teammates for their collaboration and encouragement.

Also, a **special thanks and heartfelt shoutout** goes to my friend **Atang Osik, Geetanjali Sutradhar, Kyam Panggeng, Kangee Panor, Minam Panggam and Bang Boko**, whose constant motivation, enthusiasm, and support played a significant role in keeping me focused and inspired throughout this research journey.

Abstract

This study investigates the real-world applications of mathematics among local vendors in Pasighat, examining how practical experience often complements or surpasses formal mathematical education in developing strong mathematical skills for pricing, profit-loss calculations, and customer transactions.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Literature Review	3
1.2	Objectives	4
1.3	Research Methodology	5
1.4	Preliminary	6
1.4.1	Market Visit Experience(Conversation between us)	7
2	Main Findings and Data Analysis	8
2.1	Pricing and Business Decisions	8
2.2	Profit, Loss, and Estimation Strategies	8
2.3	Calculation Methods and Mental Math	9
2.4	Record-Keeping and Use of Technology	9
2.5	Vendor Demographics and Educational Background	10
2.6	Mathematical Attitudes and Preferences	11
2.7	Sources of Learning	13
2.8	Data Visualisation:	14
2.8.1	Accuracy in Real-World Math Applications	14
2.8.2	Speed of Mental Calculation Among Vendors	15
2.9	Field Interaction with Local Vendors during Survey:	16
2.10	Summary of Vendor Insights	17
3	Discussion	18
3.1	Conclusion	19
A	Appendix A: Solved Sample Paper by Vendor	21

Keywords: Local Vendors, Real-World Mathematics, Profit and Loss, Daily Transactions, Estimation, Discount, Mental Calculation, Field Survey, Financial Literacy, Pricing Strategies, Vendor Business Practices.

MSC Subject Classification: 97M40, 97D40, 91B38, 97K60

Chapter 1

Introduction

Mathematics is a key aspect of everyday life, though its significance is often underestimated outside of formal education. While textbooks and classrooms teach the theoretical aspects of math, its practical applications play a central role in many real-world scenarios. Local vendors, who are integral to the informal economy, engage with mathematics in their day-to-day operations—whether they are aware of it or not. These vendors use math to determine prices, calculate profits, manage inventory, and track expenses. Despite their lack of formal education in mathematics, their daily experience and practice contribute to a strong mathematical ability, making experience more valuable than formal training in many cases.

This dissertation aims to explore how local vendors apply mathematics in their businesses, focusing on their real-world practices. It seeks to uncover the mathematical strategies they use, how they integrate math into their operations, and the role experience plays in shaping their mathematical skills. By understanding their methods, this study hopes to highlight the significance of practical knowledge over theoretical learning, emphasizing the value of experiential learning in enhancing mathematical ability. Furthermore, the research will provide insights into how education, or the lack thereof, impacts the mathematical efficiency of local vendors and contributes to their success in the marketplace.

1.1 Literature Review

Previous studies have shown that the mathematics practiced outside of formal education settings—especially by street vendors—is often underestimated. One influential study[2] investigated the mathematical understanding of child vendors in Brazil and emphasized how everyday cultural practices can shape cognitive development and informal mathematical skills, as published in *Child Development* under the title *The Mathematics of Child Street Vendors*.

Another relevant study[1] explored the application of mathematical concepts in small business environments, highlighting how tools such as probability and arithmetic are vital for pricing strategies, profit estimation, and financial decision-making in business contexts.

However, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding how local vendors in rural or semi-urban areas apply mathematics in daily business operations without formal education or training. This dissertation aims to address that gap by focusing on real-world, experience-based applications of mathematics among vendors in such settings.

1.2 Objectives

- To investigate how local vendors determine the prices of their products and apply mathematics in daily life.
- To understand the methods vendors use to calculate profits and losses, including mental calculations and estimation.
- To explore the ability of vendors to perform calculations without using calculators and the role of experience in business operations.
- To examine how vendors manage inventory, estimate bulk-buying costs, and track income and expenses.
- To compare the impact of formal education versus practical, real-world application of mathematics in business settings.

1.3 Research Methodology

The research was conducted through a field survey targeting local vendors from different sectors—vegetable and meat sellers, grocery shops, cyber cafés, and electronics retailers.

A mixed-method approach was used, combining both qualitative and quantitative questions to assess the vendors' use of mathematics in their day-to-day business practices.

A total of 50 vendors participated in the survey, selected from various categories based on business type, education level, and experience. Data collection involved direct interaction with respondents, mostly around markets in Pasighat. The sample included:

- 25% graduates
- 40% school dropouts
- 35% illiterate individuals

Data was categorized by business type, school type attended, and years of experience. Both quantitative and qualitative responses were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify patterns and insights into how mathematics is applied by these vendors.

1.4 Preliminary

The questionnaire used for this study was divided into three major sections:

1. **Demographic Information** – to gather details about the vendor’s background, such as age, education, and type of business.
2. **Interest in Mathematics** – to understand their attitude toward mathematics, including preferred operations and difficulty areas.
3. **Real-World Mathematical Application** – to explore how mathematics is applied in their daily business activities, such as pricing, profit-loss calculation, estimation, and use of digital tools.

Vendors were questioned about their pricing strategies, calculation methods, estimation techniques, and use of technology. Observational notes were also taken to assess their accuracy, confidence, and general mathematical behavior during real-life interactions.

Additionally, two major patterns emerged from the initial analysis:

- **Variation in Mathematical Application Across Business Types and Education Levels** – Vendors from different business types and educational backgrounds demonstrated varying levels of mathematical fluency, with vegetable and meat sellers (often with little formal education) showing strong mental math skills.
- **Limited Correlation Between Educational Qualification and Mathematical Performance** – Surprisingly, vendors with higher education often relied on calculators and were not always more efficient than their less-educated peers, highlighting the role of experience over formal schooling.

1.4.1 Market Visit Experience(Conversation between us)

Before conducting our survey among local vendors, we decided to visit the market to get a firsthand experience of the environment. During our visit, we realized that the market area is full of noise and activities, and it is not easy to approach vendors and ask them questions during busy hours. Therefore, we chose to conduct our interactions in a more calm and friendly manner rather than a formal survey style[3].

When we first approached the vendors with our printed questions, many of them ignored us. Some even said, “No time.” We realized that taking out printed sheets made it look like an official or government survey, which made vendors suspicious and reluctant to participate. So, we changed our strategy. Instead of directly showing the questionnaire, we started having casual conversations. We would buy something from them first and then gently bring up the topic, saying something like, “Bhaiya, humlog ek chhota research kar rahe hain, aapke jaise logon ke kaam ke upar. Agar aap thoda samay denge toh bahut madad milegi.” This approach helped us build trust[3].

In many cases, vendors were more comfortable talking when we stood beside them and observed how they handled customers. This way, we could notice how they calculated prices, returned change, and managed multiple items mentally. Sometimes they used a calculator, sometimes just their memory. We realized that if we had only relied on written answers, we would have missed the real essence of how mathematics is used in their daily work[3].

Many vendors laughed and said, “Humko kya maloom kitna percent profit hota hai, bas paisa milta hai toh le lete hain.” But when we rephrased our questions and talked about real examples like, “Agar 100 ka saman 120 mein bechte ho, toh kitna munafa hua?” they answered very clearly. We also discovered that most vendors don’t think in terms of “percentage” but rather in absolute values—how much they spend and how much they earn[3].

Our aim was not to confuse or test their mathematical knowledge but to understand how they use basic mathematical thinking in real-life situations. We also wanted to know if their schooling had any impact on their current practices. Many told us they had forgotten what they learned in school, but they still use similar methods like addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and approximation every day.

This preliminary experience taught us the importance of listening, observing, and respecting the vendors’ time and space. It also showed us that mathematics is not always about formulas—it’s also about logic, experience, and practical decision-making. This real-world understanding became the base for our further data collection[4].

Chapter 2

Main Findings and Data Analysis

The study reveals that local vendors use mathematics extensively in their day-to-day business operations, regardless of their educational background. Their approach to pricing, profit management, and estimation reflects not only practical knowledge but also experience-driven intuition[4].

2.1 Pricing and Business Decisions

Vendors establish their prices based on multiple factors. The most common considerations include the cost of acquisition—which covers purchasing, transportation, and storage—and the level of market competition. Vendors often monitor neighboring stalls and shops to keep their rates competitive. Additionally, customer demand plays a significant role; prices usually increase during peak seasons or for high-demand items[4].

2.2 Profit, Loss, and Estimation Strategies

To determine profit or loss, vendors subtract expenses—including cost of goods and operational overheads—from their total income. Those who experience losses tend to adjust their purchasing and pricing strategies to reduce further risk. Bulk buying is a common practice among vendors, where they estimate costs based on unit prices and consider supplier discounts. Many rely on experience and prior dealings to negotiate better deals, and haggling remains an active part of the supply process[4].

2.3 Calculation Methods and Mental Math

A significant observation from the study is the reliance on mental arithmetic among vendors, particularly vegetable and meat sellers. Despite being illiterate in some cases, these vendors can perform quick and accurate calculations without the help of calculators. They are often faster and more confident in their calculations than other vendors. In contrast, vendors in businesses such as grocery shops, bookstores, electronics, and cyber cafés typically use calculators or mobile apps to ensure accuracy, especially for larger transactions or when dealing with billing [3].

Table 2.1: Calculation Methods

Method Used	Percentage
Calculators	75%
Mental Math	25%

Analysis :

The data from the table reveals two distinct groups of vendors based on their calculation methods.

- **Calculators (75%)**: A majority of the vendors (75%) use calculators or mobile apps. This is especially common in businesses where more complex calculations are involved, such as in grocery shops, bookstores, and electronics. Vendors in these sectors tend to rely on technology to minimize errors and ensure precision, particularly when dealing with bulk items or larger sums[3].

- **Mental Math (25%)**: On the other hand, 25% of vendors, particularly those in the vegetable and meat selling businesses, use mental math to perform calculations. Despite lacking formal education in many cases, these vendors possess strong mental arithmetic skills, enabling them to handle simple and quick calculations efficiently. Their ability to perform such tasks without relying on external tools points to the importance of practical experience and adaptability in day-to-day operations[3].

The difference in the calculation methods between these two groups of vendors suggests that while technological tools are becoming increasingly common, mental arithmetic remains a valuable skill, especially for those who are less reliant on formal education.

2.4 Record-Keeping and Use of Technology

For tracking income and expenses, vendors follow varied methods. Some still use traditional notebooks or cash registers, whereas others—especially younger or more tech-exposed vendors—have adopted mobile apps for efficient financial record-keeping.

2.5 Vendor Demographics and Educational Background

The vendors interviewed represented diverse backgrounds in terms of schooling and business types [3]. This diversity allowed for a broad understanding of how education and vendor type might influence their use of mathematics in daily practices.

Table 2.2: School Type of Vendors

School Type	Percentage
Government School	50%
Private School	20%
Both	30%

Analysis:

The data shows that 50% of vendors attended government schools, while 20% studied in private schools, and 30% had exposure to both. This indicates that a large portion of vendors had their education through public institutions, possibly reflecting the general education pattern in semi-urban and rural regions. The 30% who studied in both types may have shifted between systems due to financial or family reasons[3].

Table 2.3: Vendor Types

Vendor Type	Percentage
Small-Shop/Grocery-mall / Veg-Meat seller	40%
Cyber-cafe/Electronics-cafe/Bookstores	25%
Mixed	35%

Analysis:

Regarding vendor types, 40% were engaged in smaller shops such as groceries or selling vegetables and meat, while 25% were operating more technically inclined businesses like cyber cafés, electronics shops, or bookstores. Another 35% ran mixed-type setups, combining various business elements. This variation highlights the wide scope of mathematical practices based on business nature, where product type and customer interaction differ significantly[3].

Table 2.4: Years in Business

Range of Experience
1 or (less than 1) to 30 years

Analysis:

The range of business experience varied from 1 or (less than 1) to 30 years among the vendors interviewed. This wide span of experience suggests that some vendors were just beginning while others had decades of hands-on exposure to market practices. Such differences in experience level may influence how confidently and efficiently vendors apply mathematical knowledge, regardless of their formal education background[3].

2.6 Mathematical Attitudes and Preferences

A majority of vendors expressed a positive attitude toward mathematics, despite having limited formal education in some cases [3]. Their preferences and difficulties reveal how certain operations are more intuitively grasped through experience, while others pose challenges in everyday business tasks.

Table 2.5: Interest in Mathematics

Interest Level	Percentage
Enjoy Math	70%
Neutral	10%
Not Much	5%
Do Not Enjoy	15%

Analysis:

As seen above, 70% of vendors reported enjoying mathematics. This reflects a largely positive perception, likely due to the practical nature of their engagement with numbers in daily transactions. Only 15% expressed a dislike, suggesting that for most, math is not an obstacle but a useful tool[3].

Table 2.6: Mathematical Preferences

Preferred Operation	Percentage
Addition	80%
Multiplication	15%
Subtraction	5%

Analysis:

Addition emerged as the most preferred operation, with 80% choosing it as the easiest and most frequently used. This is expected, as addition is central to pricing, totaling purchases, and giving change. Multiplication follows, especially relevant for bulk pricing, while subtraction is used less and considered more mechanical than conceptual[3].

Table 2.7: Difficult Mathematical Areas

Topic	Percentage Facing Difficulty
Division	70%
Discount	30%

Analysis:

Division stood out as the most difficult operation, with 70% of vendors expressing struggle, particularly in splitting costs or calculating unit prices from totals. Discount calculations also challenged 30% of them, often due to percentage-based reasoning or lack of structured training[3].

These findings show that while vendors are generally comfortable with day-to-day calculations, there remains a gap in understanding slightly more abstract or formal mathematical ideas like division or percentages. This also highlights the potential value of targeted informal learning or community-based education to bridge such gaps.

2.7 Sources of Learning

While vendors' day-to-day business practice plays a key role in sharpening their mathematical abilities, many still acknowledge the foundational role of formal education. The following data shows the range of sources that contributed to their mathematical learning.

Table 2.8: Source of Mathematical Learning

Learning Source	Percentage / Notes
School Teachers	91%
Internet (mostly millennial and Gen Z age)	7%
Self-study	1%
Parents	1%

Analysis:

The vast majority (91%) of vendors credited their school teachers as the primary source of their mathematical knowledge. This highlights the continuing influence of basic formal education, even in professions that rely more on practical experience than on academic qualifications.

Interestingly, 7% of vendors—primarily those from younger generations (millennials and Gen Z)—reported using the internet as a source of learning. This suggests a shift toward digital resources for reinforcement or clarification of concepts, even among those engaged in informal economic sectors.

Self-study and learning from parents were both cited by only 1% of vendors. While these are minor sources in this context, they still reflect individual efforts to acquire knowledge beyond the classroom, especially in households where business is part of family tradition[3].

Overall, this section reinforces the idea that formal education lays the groundwork for basic mathematical competence, which is then honed through continuous application in real-world vendor environments.

2.8 Data Visualisation:

2.8.1 Accuracy in Real-World Math Applications

Figure 2.1 illustrates vendor responses to three practical math questions, with results normalized out of 10 responses per question. The green bars represent correct answers, while red indicates incorrect or no responses.

Figure 2.1: Bar-Graph Representation of Vendor Accuracy in Real-World Math Tasks

Analysis:

The highest accuracy was observed in the basic arithmetic task — calculating change after purchasing rice — where 9 out of 10 vendors responded correctly. This suggests strong familiarity with everyday money-related transactions involving subtraction.

Slightly more challenging was the question on calculating a 10% discount, with 8 vendors answering correctly. This indicates that while percentage-based reasoning is still manageable for most, it may require a bit more structured understanding.

The most difficult problem involved calculating the cost of 1.6 kg of chicken at Rs550 per kg, which combines both multiplication and unit rate logic. Here, only 6 vendors gave correct responses, highlighting the challenge of dealing with decimal multiplication and real-unit pricing — a skill often not emphasized in early education or practice[3].

Overall, the data suggests that vendors are quite capable in tasks that mirror their daily experiences, but accuracy decreases as the complexity or abstraction of the problem increases.

2.8.2 Speed of Mental Calculation Among Vendors

Figure 2.2 illustrates the observed speed of mental calculation across various vendor categories. The speed score (out of 10) is based on how quickly each vendor type performed basic arithmetic operations during real-life transactions.

Figure 2.2: This graph illustrates the speed of mental calculation among different types of vendors, based on observational data. The speed score (out of 10) reflects how quickly vendors performed basic arithmetic tasks during real-life transactions.

Analysis:

The highest mental calculation speed was observed among vegetable sellers (9.5) and meat sellers (8.9), who often deal with bulk quantities, rapid bargaining, and change returns — demanding swift mental processing. Small shopkeepers also showed strong performance (7.8), as they frequently compute small totals and change manually.

In contrast, cyber cafés (7), electronic retailers (7.4), and bookstore owners (7.5) demonstrated slower response times, likely due to reliance on calculators or digital billing tools. Street food vendors showed decent mental speed (8), possibly due to constant cash handling and fast-paced sales[3].

These variations suggest that vendor type and nature of business significantly influence mental math agility.

2.9 Field Interaction with Local Vendors during Survey:

Figure 2.3: Survey Interaction with a Vegetable Vendor in Pasighat Market[3]

*For the solved sample paper, refer to **Appendix A**.*

2.10 Summary of Vendor Insights

- Vendors calculate prices based on cost, competition, and customer demand.
- Profit and loss are calculated through routine subtraction of expenses from income.
- Vegetable and meat sellers show strong mental math capabilities.
- Vendors in cyber cafés, bookstores, and groceries mostly use calculators.
- Practical experience often outweighs formal education in mathematical fluency.[4]

Chapter 3

Discussion

The findings highlight a crucial insight: formal education alone does not ensure mathematical fluency in real-life situations. Educated vendors, including graduates, often showed accuracy in calculations but sometimes lacked confidence during written responses, occasionally making spelling or presentation errors. In contrast, illiterate vendors—especially vegetable and meat sellers—performed mental calculations with remarkable speed and confidence. Their skill came not from textbooks, but from constant, hands-on experience, showing how daily practice builds intuitive mathematical understanding.

Although calculators and mobile apps are commonly used, especially by bookstore and cyber café vendors, many sellers still depend on mental math. Vegetable and meat sellers stood out as the quickest and most accurate, handling complex calculations on the spot without any tools. This not only shows strong numeracy but also sharp decision-making, developed through daily market experience rather than classroom learning.

Overall, the study reveals that mathematics is deeply embedded in the everyday operations of local vendors. Whether it's pricing items, calculating profit or loss, or managing bulk purchases, vendors apply core mathematical concepts with consistency and accuracy. These findings suggest that real-world experience plays a more powerful role than formal education in developing practical math skills, highlighting the true value of learning by doing[4].

3.1 Conclusion

The real-world application of mathematics among local vendors reveals that experience, repetition, and hands-on engagement often outweigh formal education in practical value. These vendors demonstrate that mathematics is not confined to classrooms or textbooks but is a vital tool in running small businesses. From setting prices and offering discounts to calculating profits, estimating quantities, and managing inventory, they are silent mathematicians applying concepts of arithmetic, profit and loss, percentages, estimation, and record-keeping in their daily operations.

This study highlights that their mathematical skills are not always learned formally but are developed and sharpened through daily practice and necessity. Their intuitive understanding of numbers enables them to make quick and accurate decisions that directly impact their income and customer satisfaction.

Further research could explore how the integration of digital tools, such as mobile apps and spreadsheets, enhances the accuracy and efficiency of these vendors' calculations and decision-making processes. Understanding this evolving relationship between traditional practices and digital assistance can provide deeper insights into modern-day mathematical engagement in informal economic settings[4].

Sponsor

I gratefully acknowledge the generous financial support provided by my project supervisor, **Dr. Gete Umbrey**. Their personal investment in this research, both intellectually and financially, was invaluable and deeply appreciated.

Bibliography

- [1] Jaiswal.M. *A Study of Application of Mathematics in Business, Commerce and Management*. Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research, Vol. 9, No. 6 (2022), pp. 240–245. Available at: <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2206028.pdf>
- [2] Saxe.B. *The Mathematics of Child Street Vendors*. Child Development, Vol. 59, No. 6 (1988), pp. 1415–1428. Wiley on behalf of the Society for Research in Child Development. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1130503>
- [3] Field survey data collected by the researcher.
- [4] Personal observations and suggestions from friends and elders.
- [5] Microsoft Excel, *Graph Plotting and Data Visualization*.
In this Dissertation, Microsoft Excel was utilized to plot graphs illustrating two key aspects observed among local vendors: (1) The accuracy in real-world mathe applications and (2) the speed of mental calculations during customer transactions. These graphs helped to visually analyze and compare vendor performance, making it easier to interpret data patterns and draw meaningful conclusions.
- [6] OpenAI, *ChatGPT: Language Support Tool*, 2024.
ChatGPT was used to assist with language-related tasks such as grammar correction, sentence rephrasing, and improving the overall clarity of written content in the dissertation.

Appendix A

Appendix A: Solved Sample Paper by Vendor

Page 1

Page 2

Page 3

Page 4

Page 5

Page 6

Figure A.1: Solved Sample Paper Submitted by Vendor